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Bringing the Arctic Data System to action

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The key motivation behind Arctic PASSION is to contribute to the co-creation and implementation of a coherent, integrated Arctic observing system. It aims to overcome known flaws in the present observing system by refining its operability, improving, and extending pan-Arctic scientific and community-based monitoring and the integration with Indigenous and Local knowledge. It also aims at streamlining the access and interoperability of Arctic Data systems and services and contribute to ensuring the economic viability and sustainability of the observing system.

Summary

Data about the Arctic are organised in complex systems that include many research disciplines working together. Better understanding the nature of Arctic information has been seen as valuable in its own right.

The polar data community has created organizations like the Arctic Data Committee (ADC) of the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) and the Sustaining Arctic Observing Network (SAON), the Standing Committee on Antarctic Data Management (SCADM) of the Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR) and the Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS).

In November 2014, members of the ADC recognized that an effort to create an overview of the Arctic information system would be highly relevant.

Through a number of workshops organised between the mentioned organizations, more and more information was organised in spreadsheets, and this proved to be a valuable start. Through WP2 in Arctic PASSION a more formal data model and use cases for the activity were organised. Ingestion of the data into a more specialised application both simplified maintenance of the dataset as well as the analysis.

From theoretical deliberations in the literature, it had been suggested that the information could successfully be described within a *data ecosystem* framework, where data centres are nodes, and their relationships are described as their interaction in terms of exchange of information.

Owners of data centres were contacted during summer 2024 with a request to update their information in the application. While the process of updating the information is a continuous process, this report is based on a snapshot extracted 8th October 2024.

An analysis using formal *network analysis* allowed the ranking of the most important or influential data centres in the network. A simple frequency analysis of the technical relationships between data centres showed some regional differences. The majority of data centres that have responded come from Europe and North-America, and there are regional differences in terms of interoperability protocols used for discovery metadata.

Findings from the exercise include that the methods and the system developed demonstrate that the polar data system is an interconnected ecosystem comprising many networks. For a number of years, this description was not adequately updated or maintained due to limited resources. Dedicated resources

allowed for continued development of a dedicated database and platform and engagement with the community to help support data update and curation.

Another finding is that what started as an effort for Arctic data centres and evolved into an activity of Polar data centres also acknowledged that few data centres are strictly polar. Many data centres that serve data on the polar regions are in fact more general data centres.

Proposed next steps following the exercise include that the activity undertaken could help the development of the interaction between data centres, but it should not replace the effort to organize and document the underlying datasets. The information collected shows that there are many approaches to organising data and that efforts to standardise this should continue. It is unlikely that only one approach will be used by all, but data centres should adhere to and promote a few formal standards.

Another proposed next step is to note that the theoretical, methodological and technological approach used and outlined in this report can be applied to other perspectives of interaction between actors in the Polar regions, like the exchange of information about *observing assets* (which for example is observing sites, research stations and other research platforms, and cruises) publications, software, etc. This would be a far more challenging exercise than what has been done for data centres but have a clear governance perspective both in the Antarctic and the Arctic.

1. Background

Data about the Arctic are organised in complex systems that include many research disciplines working together, Indigenous and non-Indigenous residents, rapidly evolving geo-politics and significant environmental change (Larsen and Fondahl, 2015). Better understanding the nature of Arctic information has been seen as valuable in its own right and for informing other domains and regions.

Many Arctic-relevant data centres, stewardship and policy nodes exist at the global level (i.e. World Meteorological Organization, Group on Earth Observations). These nodes typically act as umbrella organizations that coordinate activities and/or establish broad standards and specifications. Initial examinations of the national level revealed complex national systems. For example, the U.S. Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) comprises a set of seventeen government agencies and departments that have an Arctic dimension and, in many cases, produce or manage data.

Based on their complex, interdisciplinary science data management experiences during the International Polar Year 2007–2009, Parsons et al. (2011) argue that a “data ecosystem” metaphor should be used to conceptualize the polar data system. The following steps have been proposed to use the framework of *information ecology* (IE):

1. Identify information ecosystem components (e.g. data centres, datasets, funders, users)
2. Establish how components interact (e.g. sharing (meta)data, funding projects, exchanging personnel)
3. Model system dynamics (e.g. creation of synthetic products from multiple data centres, project succession, project extinction)
4. Apply understanding to real world applications (e.g. planning data services for an observing system, planning decadal-scale funding, supporting communities in disaster resilience)

The project Mapping the Arctic Data Ecosystem (MADE) was established and was documented as an example of the use of the conceptual framework of IE (Pulsifer et al, 2020). The Arctic PASSION work documented here can contribute to 1) and 2) above with a focus on digital data, and the large number of sub-systems that comprise the data system. At a later stage in development, it was decided to expand the work also to include data centres organising data from Antarctica, and the project was renamed to ‘Mapping the Polar Data Ecosystem’ (MPDE).

An application relevant to the MPDE project is supporting the implementation of the Sustaining Arctic Observing Network program (Berkman, 2015). The SAON Strategy and implementation plan includes creating a ‘roadmap’ to a well-integrated Arctic observing system (SAON, 2018). This ‘roadmap’ recognizes the need for an understanding of existing and emerging technical and human components of the Arctic *data ecosystem*. A concrete outcome of the work has been establishing the SAON Data Portal¹ (Arctic PASSION, 2022), which seeks to address the ‘F’ in the *FAIR principles*² by offering information about polar data in a *federated search* framework (Wilkinson et al., 2016). It is believed that the MPDE project will allow additional data centres to be included in the portal.

¹ <https://data.arcticobserving.org/>

² In 2016, the ‘FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship’ were published. The authors intended to provide guidelines to improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets

2. Data collection and data updating process

Polar regions are characterised by responses to significant environmental, economic and societal changes, and the *polar data ecosystem* is consequently broad and complex. Identifying, documenting and understanding the polar components of the global information system will allow targeting gaps in information resources, as well as guide the ongoing development of the increasingly interconnected global information system in support of governance, research, livelihoods and myriad other applications.

In an effort to manage this complexity, the polar data community has created organizations for the purpose of promoting and facilitating international collaboration toward improving data access and interoperability. The International Arctic Science Committee³ (IASC) and the Sustaining Arctic Observing Network⁴ (SAON) has formed the Arctic Data Committee⁵ (ADC). At the inaugural meeting held in Potsdam, Germany, in November 2014, members of the ADC recognized that an effort to create an overview of the Arctic information system would be highly relevant. In the Antarctic, the parallel organisations are the Standing Committee on Antarctic Data Management (SCADM) of the Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR) and the Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS).

The deliberations behind the *polar data ecosystem* started when ADC was established in 2014, and since then, the above-mentioned organisations have convened regularly to discuss how polar data can be more FAIR:

- The *Interoperability Workshop and Assessment Process*⁶ formulated basic ‘Polar Data Resource Requirements’, under (among other) the themes ‘Discovery and Documentation’, ‘Data as a Service’, and ‘Cloud Data and Computing Platform Interoperability’ (The Polar Data Community, 2017).
- At the *Polar Data Planning Summit*⁷, the focus was on how to develop international data sharing case studies or scenarios.
- The *Polar Data and Systems Architecture Workshop*⁸ documented technical aspects of the *polar data ecosystem* (e.g. (meta)data services, sharing protocols, vocabularies etc.).

The two latter meetings resulted in a spreadsheet describing metadata sharing interactions between data centres (i.e. who was harvesting information from whom), information about which interoperability standards were used, etc. This spreadsheet was later developed jointly by the *Working group on Federated Search for Polar Regions*⁹ and the *Polar Semantics Working Group*¹⁰.

Throughout the period, it was realised that the spreadsheet solution to organize the information was not satisfactory. Within the framework of Arctic PASSION Work Package 2, a more systematic approach to maintaining the information was initiated, and a dedicated technical platform was developed (see Chapter 3).

³ <http://iasc.info>

⁴ <https://www.arcticobserving.org>

⁵ <https://arcticdc.org>

⁶ Frascati, Italy, 2016: <https://www.arcticdc.org/meetings/conferences/interoperability-workshop>

⁷ Boulder, Colorado, 2018: <https://www.arcticdc.org/meetings/conferences/polar-data-planning-summit>

⁸ Geneva, Switzerland, 2018: <https://arcticdc.org/meetings/conferences/polar-data-architecture-workshop>

⁹ <https://arcticdc.org/activities/core-projects/federated-search>

¹⁰ <https://arcticdc.org/activities/core-projects/vocabularies-and-semantics-wg>

At the onset of Arctic PASSION WP2 work, approximately 80 data centres and their relationships had been identified. Individuals at these data centres were contacted by mail in order to confirm that they were indeed responsible for the data centres. If this was confirmed, users were given credentials, allowing them to login and update information in the platform.

This update process was launched in July 2024 and ran until September 2024. Through this period, information about 29 data centres was updated by the users and information about 13 data centres was updated by the system administrator. New data centres were added, and a total of 96 data centres were included in the system. A total of 185 harvesting links were included in the system at the end of the period, and 51 of these links were created or updated by users, and 2 edits were made by the system administrator. These and other statistics are continuously being updated at the system statistics page¹¹.

3. Technical platform and data model

The information collected in the project can be organised in a so-called *linked open data* model to describe the components (*nodes*) and relationships (*edges*) in the system model. This approach is well suited to representing networks and systems as it uses a *graph* model to store and model data. In this context, a *graph* is a network of *nodes* linked together by an *edge*. *Nodes* in this context are *data catalogues*, and *edges* are relationships (in this case *shares metadata with*) (Pulsifer et al., 2020).

In creating the representation, wherever possible the MPDE project has been aiming to use existing vocabularies or ontologies that have a significant level of adoption to define concepts and relationships. This provides the best chance of achieving interoperability with other projects in the future. It is important to note that many vocabularies or ontologies in use are being developed dynamically and are “living” entities that provide options for review and modification. In the case where an appropriate ontology does not exist, the project has defined its own and is making it available along with documentation so that others can understand the terms and relationships.

In order to have a better basis for further development of the mapping activity and ease maintenance of the technical platform, it was decided to develop a data model for the application. This data model should support a wide variety of use cases as well as also support efficient and transparent maintenance of the information collected. In the process of establishing this data model, it has been decided that the content of the mapping activity also shall be available under a CC-BY-4.0 license¹². The data model is developed and maintained through the GitHub platform¹³.

To make the representation model accessible to non-expert users, the MPDE project developed a dynamic visualization tool (Figure 1). This tool allows a user to view the graph in its entirety or in parts. There is a query facility that will allow users to query the system to establish, for example, which data centres are sharing data using a particular protocol.

¹¹ <https://mpde.gcrc.carleton.ca/stats.html>

¹² <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.en>

¹³ <https://github.com/POLDER-Crew/PDEMDataModel>

Figure 1: The graph shows the harvesting relationships among data catalogues that contain data relevant to the polar regions. It shows the network of systems and how data is harvested from one system to another. Edges in the graph denote harvesting with arrows pointing toward the organization that consumes the harvest. Colours denote the state of the harvesting: Green: Present; Orange: Planned; Blue: Past; Red: Complicated; Grey: Unknown. The graph is interactive and can be further explored at https://mpde.gcrc.carleton.ca/index.html?module=module.harvest_link_graph

The first-generation database and visualization tool was created at the University of Colorado and provided basic data exploration functions. A more functional, established, open-source platform was desired to continue the migration from a simple spreadsheet to a database management and visualization platform. The next technical platform to organize the information in the MPDE project was developed using the Nunaliit Atlas Framework¹⁴ (Hayes and Taylor, 2019). The goal of the framework is to make it easy to tell stories and highlight relationships between many different forms of information from a variety of sources, using maps and visualizations as a central way to connect and interact with the data. The code for the system is under a license that permits broad adoption of the software and encourages use of the ideas as widely as possible. The New BSD License¹⁵ permits use, redistribution, and modification by anyone with no obligation to make the modifications available for others.

4. Analysis and discussion of collected data

A summary of the data collected is available through the platform statistics web page¹⁶. Organising the information in the exercise is an ongoing process, but a version of the underlying database was exported on 8th October 2024. In this version, information about a total of 96 data catalogues was organised during the exercise, and a total of 185 harvesting relationships were documented¹⁷. The overview of the

¹⁴ <https://nunaliit.org/>

¹⁵ <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/GCRC/nunaliit/master/license.txt>

¹⁶ <https://mpde.gcrc.carleton.ca/stats.html>

¹⁷ https://mpde.gcrc.carleton.ca/index.html?module=module.harvest_link_list

information collected is found in Appendix A. Table A.1 gives an overview of the information organised for the data catalogues, while table A.2 gives an overview of the information organised for the harvesting relations.

4.1 Frequency statistics

The status and the technical nature of the metadata harvesting relationships were of particular interest, and simple frequencies of the information were calculated (Appendix B).

Users could provide information about the actual status of the harvesting, and about two-thirds reported that it was ongoing (Table B.1, 'At present', 61%). Other response options were 'In past', 'In planning', and 'It's complicated'. The latter was reported in 18% of the cases. Information about harvesting frequency was only provided by a minority of users, and the most frequent response was 'Daily' (Table B.2, 78%).

One of the most important purposes of the exercise is to better understand the technical standards used for the harvesting. For the *harvesting protocol* used, only a minority of users had provided this information, and the most frequent response was OAI-PMH (Table B.3, 42%). Similarly, for the *metadata standard* used, only a minority of users had provided this information, and the most frequent response was *schema.org* (Table B.4, 33%).

In these statistics, it is important to emphasise that even so-called "standards" are evolving along the lines of ecosystem development, as noted by Pulsifer et al. (2020).

4.2 Network analysis

Social network analysis (SNA) is the process of investigating social structures through the use of networks and graph theory. It characterizes networked structures in terms of *nodes* (individual actors, people, or things within the network) and the *links* (relationships or interactions) that connect them. Examples of social structures commonly visualized through *social network analysis* include social media networks, friendship and acquaintance networks, business networks, knowledge networks, collaboration graphs and other.

This network analysis uses the *SNoMaN* package in RStudio. This allows for visualization of the MPDE network's distribution globally and to determine regionally the clustering and influence of organizations through their harvesting relationships. The following tables and graphs visualize these relationships in various ways.

Table 1: Basic relationships based on global region. *Source connections* are classified as providing data while *Aggregator connections* are the target from the source that compiles data. *Note:* Some repositories are both source and aggregators.

Region	Source connections	Aggregator connections
Americas	80	81
Asia/Oceania	38	16
Europe/Africa	67	88

Table 2: Harvesting technology mapped by frequency/use broken down by region.

Region	OAI-PMH	OGC CSW	schema.org	Other
Americas	2	1	7	1
Arctic	5	1	4	0
Asia/Oceania	2	0	1	0
Europe/Africa	5	2	2	1

The two tables are basic statistics based on world regions. Table 1 includes both source and target repository relationships. All repositories have the ability to be included as a source and/or aggregator. This can provide insight into areas in need of further support and/or regions that have not participated in the project. Not all repositories are included as there were 3 nodes that did not provide any location data (latitude, longitude). Table 2 highlights the common technologies used for harvesting based on the location of the repository region (OAI-PMH/OGC CSW/schema.org/Other). Not all repositories included this technical information in the input field within the MPDE system. Only the repositories that did provide their harvesting technology information were included and added to the table, and the snapshot was from aggregator repositories. To further understand the relationships between the repositories currently in the MPDE database, Figure 2 below shows the repositories plotted globally and the lines display the relationship between these organizations.

Network of Source and Aggregator Repositories on World Map

Figure 2: Map of network relationships between source and aggregator repositories. Note: Not all repositories had a coordinate listed and those are not represented in this figure.

Figure 2 displays a high density of repositories and organizations located in North America and Europe. To further investigate the impact of repositories and their influence on the harvesting relationships within the network, we have delved further into the network analysis. Further analysis is used to determine the high closeness centrality of participating nodes in the MPDE project. In the context of a repository network, a repository with high closeness centrality might be a central repository or an aggregator that serves as a key hub for data exchanges, enabling faster and more direct access across the network. High closeness centrality in a network indicates that a node (in this case, a repository) is relatively "close" to all other nodes in terms of the shortest paths within the network.

Social network analysis also allows an analysis of the *centrality* of nodes, where nodes with a high closeness centrality can be referred to as "hubs" or "connectors" (Barabasi and Frangos, 2014) (Table 3). Specifically, a high closeness centrality value suggests that:

- Proximity to Others: The repository can reach others with fewer intermediary connections. In practical terms, it is "well-connected" and can quickly interact with other repositories within the network.
- Efficient Information Flow: Repositories with high closeness centrality are positioned to disseminate or gather information efficiently. They have shorter average distances to other nodes, which can make them effective for data-sharing and collaboration.
- Potential Influence: Nodes with high closeness centrality are often considered influential in spreading information or resources throughout the network, as they have fewer "degrees of separation" from other nodes.

Table 3: High closeness centrality table of repositories in the MPDE database using SNoMaN. **Degree Centrality** is a measure used in network analysis to indicate the importance or influence of a node (or actor) within a network; **Closeness Centrality** is a network metric that measures how close a node is to all other nodes in the network. It reflects the node's ability to access the rest of the network quickly, indicating efficiency in spreading information or influence; **Betweenness Centrality** is a measure in network analysis that quantifies the extent to which a node lies on the shortest paths between other nodes. It indicates the role of a node in controlling the flow of information or resources across the network. Note: Only the 10 repositories with the highest **Degree Centrality** are included, and the full list can be found in Appendix C.

Repository Name	Degree Centrality	Closeness Centrality	Betweenness Centrality
DataONE	0.3452	0.3131	0.0161
Polar Data Catalogue (PDC)	0.2857	0.1925	0.0497
SAON Data Portal	0.2024	0.2172	0.0000
Group on Earth Observations System of Systems (GEOSS)	0.1548	0.2002	0.0209
Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System (SIOS)	0.1548	0.1736	0.0119
Ocean Biogeographic Information System (OBIS)	0.1310	0.1138	0.0151
Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)	0.1310	0.1151	0.0062
Global Cryosphere Watch (GCW)	0.1310	0.1953	0.0000
PANGAEA	0.1310	0.0000	0.0000
Arctic Spatial Data Infrastructure (ASDI)	0.1071	0.1472	0.0123

4.3 Additional information on harvesting links and interfaces

In addition to the systematic information about repositories and their harvesting relationships, users had also provided written text comments to the harvesting relationships. General findings among these include:

- While there tends to be a use of standard protocols for the harvesting of metadata from sources, there is little or no standardisation when it comes to interoperability at the actual data/dataset level. In many cases there is only access to metadata, but not to the actual data/dataset level.
- Metadata at sources are often incomplete.
- The relationships between organizations and repositories harvesting often rely on manual transfer processes rather than automated processes.
 - Manual intervention is often needed in the absence of automated or robust machine interfaces.

- In some cases, it is known that harvesting relationships were once set-up, but have been discontinued.
- The dataset used were missing some information for some repositories, and not all repositories supplied geographic coordinates (latitude, longitude). Those repositories were not included in figure 2 above.

5. Lessons Learned and Ways Forward

5.1 Lessons learned

The original idea of this activity was to understand relations between data centres in the Arctic. Quite early the concept of an ecosystem of linked data centres was used to describe the activity. Initial data collection was done through a number of workshops (see Chapter 2). This was an efficient approach to get the community together and establish the core dataset. As the activity evolved, so did the richness of what was captured in the dataset. The initial data collection was done through notes at workshops that were transferred into spreadsheets, and while this was an efficient approach initially, it soon became a bottleneck for handling and expanding the data. Ingestion of the data into a more specialised application both simplified maintenance of the dataset as well as the analysis. The development of a more formal data model and use cases for the activity was done after transfer of data into the application. It would probably have been beneficial to have this earlier in the process as it established a common basis for the development and paved the way for the expansion of use cases and efficient development of functionality in the application. It was only after the application was opened for contributing data centres to update their information that the content really evolved after the initial data collection.

While the exercise started as an effort for Arctic data centres and evolved into an activity of Polar data centres, it is also acknowledged that few data centres are strictly polar. Many data centres that serve data on the polar regions are in fact more general data centres. Examples of such are e.g. the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), the Copernicus services in Europe, space agencies, World Meteorological Organisation (through WMO Information System) and many more. There are also aggregating efforts like Group on Earth Observations System of Systems (GEOSS) that include polar data. None of these latter are captured in the analysis performed here so it is worth noting that what happens with data management in the polar regions are not disconnected from what is done in this area elsewhere.

It is also important to remember that the activity undertaken should help the development of the interaction between nodes in the ecosystem, but it does not replace the effort to organize and document datasets. The material collected shows that there are many approaches to sharing information between nodes in the system. There are even more approaches to sharing the actual data. For data consumers this is challenging. As it is neither feasible nor necessarily beneficial to put all data into one system it is important to enable the systems available to ‘talk’ together, also known as interoperability. Mapping exercises like this can help focus efforts at data centres, both at the discovery and use levels, and improve the interoperability between data centres. It is unlikely that only one approach is used by everyone, but data centres should adhere to and promote some formal standards. In addition, there should be a limited number of standards in use as it is then possible to bridge between these and provide better services to data consumers. This will also be a cost control effort as data management has a cost. As time passes,

new technology arises, and utilisation of this is in the interest of data consumers, but some principles for adoption (e.g. clear governance structures and consistency of standards) should be established. As seen in section 4.2, there are regional differences on what standards are adopted (e.g. schema.org is more adopted in North America and OGC CSW more in Europe). Lessons learned from e.g. ISO-19115 also show that identifying a standard is not sufficient: Usually, guidance on how to use the standard is also needed and increasingly important.

This project highlighted the need for concrete human and funding resources to make progress in the area of data management and sharing. The methods and system developed demonstrate that the polar data system is an interconnected ecosystem comprising many networks. For a number of years, valuable data describing parts of this ecosystem were not adequately updated or maintained due to limited resources. Dedicated resources allowed for continued development of a dedicated database and platform and engagement with the community to help support data update and curation.

5.2 Ways forward

Initially, the focus of the exercise was on the exchange of *discovery metadata* between data centres. However, *discovery metadata* convey information about datasets and how to access these. Thus, the information captured was expanded to understand how the actual data are shared. This perspective evolved from discovery to also cover the use perspectives of data. But equally relevant as this are other perspectives of data: The most obvious effort would probably be *polar observing assets* (which for example is observing sites, research stations and other research platforms, cruises). In these areas, information is also organised in catalogues. Work is ongoing on this in the SAON *Polar Observing Assets Working Group*¹⁸ (POAwg), which is developing the *Registry of Polar Observing Networks*¹⁹ (RoPON). Current work by this group provides a good overview, but currently, linkages between nodes in the network observing network are not collected.

The theoretical, methodological and technological approach used and outlined in this report can be applied to many such perspectives of interaction between actors in the Polar regions. This would be a far more challenging exercise than what has been done for data centres but have a clear governance perspective both in the Antarctic and Arctic. However, it is probably wise to have a focused perspective for such mapping activities and dedicated data models and use cases to fulfil.

Another perspective to analyse could be how datasets, *observing assets*, publications, software etc are linked. Or how data are linked with e.g. Shared Arctic Variables and benefits communities in the polar regions. This latter aspect of how data are transformed through services to useful information to actors is for the time being a theoretical exercise but nonetheless an emerging requirement from consumers. This implies that the data publication process has to shift focus from the needs of the data provider to a value chain approach that links data providers and data consumers (of various types).

Exercises like this mapping exercise can offer guidance for the organic development of the polar data ecosystem by ensuring timely adoption of new technologies and the provision of useful services for data consumers.

¹⁸ <https://www.polarobservingassets.org/>

¹⁹ <https://polarobservingregistry.org/>

Engagement of the non-polar data management players mentioned above has not been done consistently in this exercise and should probably be addressed from now on. How to engage these activities is to be discussed. It could be addressed from the data provider perspective instead of the aggregator perspective that has been used in the effort so far.

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<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S187396522300035X>

Appendix A. Overview of collected information

The tables below provide an overview of the information collected. The complete data model is documented in GitHub

Table A.1 Data Catalogue information

Catalogue description: Name, Alias, Description, URL	Basic information and description of the catalogue
Catalogue contact information: Name, Email, Phone Number	Basic information for catalogue contact
Geometry	The physical location of the data catalogue

Table A.2 Harvesting relationships

Harvesting Status	The current status of the harvesting, whether it is planned, ongoing, or historical, etc.
Harvesting Frequency	The time interval between (incremental) harvests from an external source.
Harvesting Protocol	The interoperability protocol used to harvest discovery metadata
Metadata Standard	The documentation standard for discovery metadata harvested
Content Aggregated	Describes whether all available records from a catalogue or subsets are harvested.
Data Access	Describes interoperability standards for direct data access as conveyed through the discovery metadata harvested and utilised by the aggregating catalogue.

Appendix B. 'Frequency statistics'

Table B.1. Harvesting Status. The current status of the harvesting, whether it is planned, ongoing, or historical, etc

	Frequency	Percent
At present	113	61
In past	14	8
In planning	24	13
It's complicated	33	18

Missing = 1

Table B.2. Harvesting Frequency. The time interval between (incremental) harvests from an external source

	Frequency	Percent
Multiple times a day	2	3
Daily	54	78
Weekly	7	10
Monthly	1	1
Irregularly	2	3
Manual	1	1
Other	2	3

Missing = 116

Table B.3. Harvesting Protocol. The interoperability protocol used to harvest discovery metadata

	Frequency	Percent
OAI-PMH	18	42
OGC CSW	4	9
schema.org	15	35
THREDDS	2	5
Other	4	9

Missing = 142

Table B.4. Metadata Standard. The documentation standard for discovery metadata harvested

	Frequency	Percent
Darwin Core Standard (Dwc)	4	9
GCMD-DIF	11	24
ISO (19115)	11	24
schema.org	15	33
Other	5	11

Missing = 139

Appendix C.

High closeness centrality table of repositories in the MPDE database using SNoMaN. **Degree Centrality** is a measure used in network analysis to indicate the importance or influence of a node (or actor) within a network; **Closeness Centrality** is a network metric that measures how close a node is to all other nodes in the network. It reflects the node's ability to access the rest of the network quickly, indicating efficiency in spreading information or influence; **Betweenness Centrality** is a measure in network analysis that quantifies the extent to which a node lies on the shortest paths between other nodes. It indicates the role of a node in controlling the flow of information or resources across the network.

For further discussion of the table - see section 4.2.

Repository Name	Degree Centrality	Closeness Centrality	Betweenness Centrality
DataONE	0.3452	0.3131	0.0161
Polar Data Catalogue (PDC)	0.2857	0.1925	0.0497
SAON Data Portal	0.2024	0.2172	0.0000
Group on Earth Observations System of Systems (GEOSS)	0.1548	0.2002	0.0209
Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System (SIOS)	0.1548	0.1736	0.0119
Ocean Biogeographic Information System (OBIS)	0.1310	0.1138	0.0151
Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)	0.1310	0.1151	0.0062
Global Cryosphere Watch (GCW)	0.1310	0.1953	0.0000
PANGAEA	0.1310	0.0000	0.0000
Arctic Spatial Data Infrastructure (ASDI)	0.1071	0.1472	0.0123
Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (CAFF)	0.1071	0.1335	0.0270
National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC)	0.1071	0.0000	0.0000
Arctic Data Center (ADC)	0.0833	0.0401	0.0060
North Slope Science Initiative (NSSI)	0.0833	0.2799	0.0000
KNB Data Repository	0.0833	0.0544	0.0057
Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Office (BCO-DMO)	0.0714	0.0214	0.0093

Rolling Deck to Repository (R2R)	0.0714	0.0357	0.0067
Polar Data Search	0.0714	0.2233	0.0000
Australian Antarctic Data Centre (AADC)	0.0714	0.0000	0.0000
Polardex	0.0595	0.1368	0.0000
Norwegian Scientific Data Network	0.0595	0.0595	0.0000
CLIVAR and Carbon Hydrographic Data Office (CCHDO)	0.0595	0.0000	0.0000
Norwegian Polar Data Centre	0.0595	0.0000	0.0000
Open Data (Canada)	0.0595	0.1335	0.0051
Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS) Antarctic	0.0595	0.0357	0.0003
National Institute of Polar Research (NIPR)	0.0476	0.0000	0.0000
Alaska Ocean Observing System (AOOS)	0.0476	0.0000	0.0000
NorthWest Territories (NWT) Discovery Portal	0.0476	0.1335	0.0010
Swedish Biodiversity Data Infrastructure (SBDI)	0.0476	0.1004	0.0000
EUDAT B2FIND	0.0476	0.1353	0.0025
Netherlands Polar Data Center (NPDC)	0.0476	0.0238	0.0006
SeaDataNet European Directory of Marine Environmental Data sets (EDMED)	0.0476	0.0268	0.0034
SCAR Antarctic Biodiversity Portla	0.0476	0.1468	0.0000
NERSC	0.0357	0.0000	0.0000
UK Polar Data Centre (UK PDC)	0.0357	0.0000	0.0000
Marlin (CSIRO)	0.0357	0.0000	0.0000
Australian Ocean Data Network (AODN)	0.0357	0.0238	0.0001
Norwegian Marine Data Centre	0.0357	0.0000	0.0000
Norwegian Meteorological Institute	0.0357	0.0000	0.0000

Atmospheric Radiation Measurement Data Center (ARM)	0.0357	0.0000	0.0000
Swedish National Data service (SND)	0.0357	0.0000	0.0000
Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring	0.0357	0.0000	0.0000
ISAAFFIK - the arctic gateway	0.0357	0.1397	0.0062
NILU	0.0357	0.0000	0.0000
NASA Arctic-Boreal Vulnerability Experiment (ABOVE)	0.0357	0.0000	0.0000
Dept. Fisheries and Oceans Canada	0.0238	0.1284	0.0002
Polish Polar Database	0.0238	0.0000	0.0000
IGPAS	0.0238	0.0000	0.0000
National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON)	0.0238	0.0000	0.0000
Environmental Data Initiative	0.0238	0.0000	0.0000
U.S. Antarctic Program Data Center (USAP-DC)	0.0238	0.2023	0.0000
Dryad	0.0238	0.0419	0.0000
British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC)	0.0238	0.0000	0.0000
ICES (geo.ices)	0.0238	0.0119	0.0001
WGMS	0.0238	0.0000	0.0000
USGS ScienceBase	0.0238	0.0000	0.0000
CNR	0.0238	0.0000	0.0000
Canadian Integrated Ocean Observing System	0.0238	0.0238	0.0000
The Home of the U.S. Government's Open Data	0.0238	0.0238	0.0000
Canadian Watershed Information Network	0.0238	0.1020	0.0004
Research Data Archive - University Corporation for Atmospheric Research and National Center for Atmospheric Research (RDA UCAR NCAR)	0.0238	0.0000	0.0000

Joint Technical Committee of Marine Meteorology Platform Support Centre (JCOMMOPS)	0.0238	0.0119	0.0001
NCEI - World Data System Paleoclimatology Data (NCEI WDS-Paleo)	0.0238	0.0238	0.0000
The Southern Ocean Observing System	0.0119	0.0000	0.0000
Long Term Ecological Research Network (LTERN)	0.0119	0.0000	0.0000
Korea Polar Data Center	0.0119	0.0000	0.0000
INTERACT GIS	0.0119	0.0000	0.0000
DataverseNO	0.0119	0.0000	0.0000
NCPOR Data Centre	0.0119	0.0000	0.0000
Arctic Research Mapping Application	0.0119	0.0000	0.0000
Scholars Portal Dataverse/OCUL/U. of Toronto	0.0119	0.1307	0.0000
The Digital Archaeological Record (tDAR)	0.0119	0.0000	0.0000
EarthChem	0.0119	0.0000	0.0000
Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost (GTN-P)	0.0119	0.0000	0.0000
Earth Observation Laboratory - University Corporation for Atmospheric Research and National Center for Atmospheric Research (EOL UCAR NCAR)	0.0119	0.0000	0.0000
The Council of Managers of National Antarctic Programs	0.0119	0.0000	0.0000
Arctic Institute of North America (AINA)	0.0119	0.0000	0.0000
Ocean Networks Canada	0.0119	0.0000	0.0000
Interact Polar Data Catalogue	0.0119	0.0119	0.0000
Swedish Species Observation Service (SOS)	0.0119	0.0000	0.0000
International Arctic Systems for Observing the Atmosphere (IASOA)	0.0119	0.0119	0.0000
NIVA	0.0119	0.0000	0.0000
GEOTRACES	0.0119	0.0000	0.0000

Appendix D. Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation	URL (where relevant)
DwC	Darwin Core Standard	http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc.htm
IE	Information Ecology	
ISO (19 115)	International Organization for Standardization (ISO) standar ISO 19115: Geographic information - Metadata standard	https://www.fgdc.gov/metadata/iso-standards
GCMD-DIF	NASA's Global Change Master Directory - Directory Interchange Format	https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/news/feature-articles/global-change-master-directory-data-services-tools-serving-international
MADE	Mapping the Arctic Data Ecosystem	
MPDE	Mapping the Polar Data Ecosystem	
OAI-PMH	The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting	https://www.openarchives.org/pmh
OGC CSW	Open Geospatial Consortium - Catalogue Services for the Web	http://opengeospatial.github.io/e-learning/cat/text/main.html
PIE	Polar Information Ecosystem	
schema.org	schema.org is a reference website that publishes documentation and guidelines for using structured data mark-up on web-pages	https://schema.org/
THREDDS Data Server (TDS)	Thematic Real-time Environmental Distributed Data Services	https://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/tds/

